

GENERAL FACTORS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE SCIENCE OF BIOLOGY AND GENETICS IN HIGHER EDUCATIONAL INSTITUTIONS

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Abstract

Based on the analyzes presented in the article, the integration of biology and genetics in the educational system affects the formation of cognitive and functional relations. As a result, it determines that man will have a stronger impact on the biosphere in terms of material, energy and information.

We will analyze the conceptual application and justification of the system created for the development of students' culture based on the integration of biology and genetics, as well as the characteristics of the main factors that determine this development, as well as the important aspects and conditions of its results in the form of the system being created.

Islam Karimov, the first President of Uzbekistan, who from the first years of independence came up with the idea of raising a healthy generation and morally improving the society, the next biggest and most important task of our state and society is the education of young people, and now our educational and educational work He stated that his priority is to ensure the mental, physical, and ideological health of the young generation, who are the future of Uzbekistan. In particular, our president said in his historical work "The main principles of the political, social and economic perspective of Uzbekistan": "We must raise a healthy generation and bring it to adulthood. By a healthy person, we understand not only physical health, but also a person who has matured in the spirit of oriental morals and universal ideas. In the future, Uzbekistan should impress the world not only with its highly developed economy, but also with its educated, spiritually mature children. I am sure that our country will turn into a land of brave and selfless people, a holy place where compassion and love are stable, where thinking and creativity boil", he said [1.2].

Today, the future that our president dreamed of and expressed his confidence in has begun to bear its fruits. Our youth have made great achievements at the international level and are raising the flag of Uzbekistan on the world stage, singing the national anthem. The main reason for the achieved achievements is undoubtedly due to the educational policy aimed at educating the young generation based on a healthy lifestyle [3].

As Doctor of Philosophical Sciences K. O. Shaykhova noted, "The most urgent sacred task that is currently in the attention of our government and its leadership is a healthy, morally perfect, humanly mature, legal deep, deeply mastering the heritage of our ancestors, people. , is aimed at educating the healthy generation, faithful to the traditions of the nation, able to ensure the stability of the Motherland, patriotic, hardworking, brave and energetic, strong-willed young people" [10].

It is known that multi-generational signs are clearly expressed in the Uzbek family. The adults of the family - grandfathers, grandmothers, close relatives, neighbors, and the

neighborhood - directly participate in the formation of healthy ideas and knowledge in the child's mind. According to our age-old customs, grandparents, grandmothers, neighbors and relatives have a stronger influence on the education of our children than parents. They are the determinants of the spiritual environment in the family. This kind of education tradition is considered an important spiritual and pedagogical value left over from the past, and this kind of education style was formed in the life of our great ancestors and reached the level of a certain system [5].

When we refer to educational knowledge, a problem is understood as a complex knowledge issue that requires learning. If we talk about simple knowledge, then it often means a practical question that is difficult to solve as a problem. And finally, if the problem is related to objective reality, then a conflict, contradiction, crisis, disaster that leads to the disruption of the successful development of events and even the threat of destruction is understood [5.9].

By activation, we understand the process of manifestation of relevance, which, in turn, means the necessity, importance, significance of a certain event that meets the most important requirements of our time.

On the other hand, ecological and valeological education aimed at developing rational and responsible relations of a growing person towards nature, society, and himself is appropriate.

Thus, the relevance of biology-genetics educational problems (and, in particular, the biology-genetics readiness of pedagogues) is a result of the integration of biology-genetics and educational problems.[4.8]

In addition, "integration of diversity" (which often occurs as a result of synergistic effect) helps to effectively solve problems with the help of biological education compared to the opportunities of general biological education [4 .6].

However, in addition to this problem, which is called relevant for our research, there are other relevant accompanying biological problems that cannot but affect the research process and therefore complicate it.

Summary. Most biology and genetics teachers in higher education institutions suggest that the relationship between man and nature can be used as a tool to change the trends of sustainable human development. It is especially important in kindergartens and schools, at the stage of the formation of children as a whole person, when it is used in the science of biology. In the biological concept, health is the ability of the human body to maintain its activity in changing conditions. That's kind of the standard we have to reach.

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